

Assessment of Bottle-Feeding Practices Among Caregivers in the Community of Karachi, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Background: Bottle feeding is an alternate technique that enables infants to get the nutrition they need to grow and develop normally. It becomes essential when breastfeeding is not possible for various reasons, including problems with the mother's health, a lack of milk supply, or individual circumstances. **Objectives:** This study aims to assess bottle-feeding practices among caregivers in the community of Karachi, Pakistan. **Methodology:** This study utilized a cross-sectional home-to-home survey design to assess bottle-feeding practices among caregivers in the community of Karachi, Pakistan. A random 30 caregivers of infants aged 1 to 12 months were selected for the study. Moreover, an adopted bottle practice assessment tool was used for the data collection. **Results:** The Study revealed that 36.7% of the individuals demonstrate Poor Practice, while 23.3% Moderate Practice and 40.0% have Good Practice. Moreover, analysis reveals a significant association between the age of caregivers and practice scores, with caregivers aged 25-30 scoring the highest p-value of 0.001. As well as that there is a significant association between the sex of the infant and practice scores p-value of 0.018. However, there is no significant association between the relation with the infant or infant age, caregivers' education, and practice scores. **Conclusion:** The results indicate that a significant number of people need to enhance their caregiving practice.

Keywords: Assessment, Bottle-Feeding, Practices, Caregivers.

Cite as:

INTRODUCTION

Bottle-feeding (BF) is feeding a baby any liquid that isn't breast milk or semi-solid food through a bottle (Batista, Ribeiro, Nascimento, & Rodrigues, 2018). Worldwide, bottle feeding as a breastfeeding substitute should be avoided due to its adverse effects on full and ideal breastfeeding and complementary eating. Breast milk substitutes are widely utilized. Additionally, because feeding bottles are difficult to keep clean, particularly in low-income and developing nations where sanitation is inadequate, they are linked to diarrheal disease morbidity and mortality in children under five. Avoiding artificial pacifiers and teats is a crucial tactic for promoting universal breastfeeding. Moreover, children's common breastfeeding issues have been linked to infants' exposure to and introduction of bottle feeding. This is related to nipple confusion, which happens when babies are exposed to two different feeding techniques, breast, and bottle, and causes the baby to refuse to nurse, decreasing the amount of milk that women produce and resulting in unsatisfactory nursing (Black et al., 2013; Organization, 2018; WHO, USAID, & AED, 2008).

The first 1000 days of a person's life, including the first two years of life and nine months of pregnancy, are considered critical, according to the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) (Hassan, Taha, Abdulla, Ali, & Adam, 2019). Malnutrition and its negative consequences, such as morbidity (diarrhea and respiratory tract infections) and mortality, are more likely to affect an unfed kid (Mahgoub & Adam, 2012). The World Health Organization (WHO) created a series of recommendations to save children's lives, including exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months and avoiding bottle-feeding, safe supplemental foods at six months, and encouraging mothers to follow these recommendations (Organization, 2017). Numerous studies showed that breastfed infants had more intellectual quotients and better cognitive development than bottle-fed babies (Hassan et al., 2019). Previous research has demonstrated that bottle feeding significantly contributed to child morbidity and mortality in various contexts (Hsu, Wu, Bornehag, Sundell, & Su, 2012; Hussain & Khan, 2017). For instance, bottle-fed infants in the Philippines were discovered to have a greater incidence of infection-related hospitalization (Hengstermann et al., 2010).

Different countries have different bottle-feeding rates, ranging from 15% in Nigeria (Ogbo, Agho, & Page, 2015) in Iraq to 64% (Network, 2015). Mothers gave various reasons for using bottles to feed their babies, including their illnesses and problems with their breasts. They imagined problems (such as believing their milk supply was inadequate) (Lokare & Hippargi, 2016). Moreover, specifically when women had difficulties breastfeeding, breastfeeding was not an option. For mothers unable to breastfeed owing to various factors, such as a low milk supply, medical conditions, or personal situations, bottle feeding becomes an option (Brown, Raynor, & Lee, 2011). Milk and other liquids are routinely provided in bottles, including semi-solid cereals when diluted with water or milk. The detrimental effects of bottle-feeding practice are particularly severe in low-income settings and developing countries due to a lack of access to clean water, sanitation, and hygiene and a high percentage of illiteracy among mothers and guardians. The level of inappropriate bottle practices and low-quality bottle treatments worsens the situation in underdeveloped nations (Chakona, 2020). More than only milk that has been overly diluted, bottle contamination and bottle-feeding dangers contribute significantly to improper feeding, which can cause malnutrition and stunted growth (Hunde, Sitotaw, & Elema, 2023).

Additionally, it increases their risk of developing gastrointestinal tract (GIT) infections, ear infections, allergic reactions, tooth decay, and other nutrition-related illnesses like diarrhea (Hunde et al., 2023). Infants who are bottle-fed are coerced by their parents or caretakers to finish the bottle, increasing their risk of gastrointestinal (GI) illnesses and exposing them to childhood obesity and diabetes mellitus compared to kids who are breastfed exclusively (Li, Magadia, Fein, & Grummer-Strawn, 2012; Li, Scanlon, May, Rose, & Birch, 2014; Taye, Asegidew, Taderegew, Bizuwork, & Zegeye, 2021). Caregivers play a significant role in ensuring infants receive appropriate and safe nutrition through bottle feeding (Spill et al., 2019). Therefore, this is necessary to assess their practice regarding bottle feeding.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A study was conducted in Bangladesh in 2020. The study found that knowledge and practice fall considerably desirable. Increasing community awareness could change the unhealthful practices of bottle feeding (Akteruzzaman et al., 2020). Additionally, another study conducted in Pakistan in 2020 found that more than 95% of the mothers were knowledgeable about feeding. However, they did not appropriately apply it to their practices (Haq et al., 2020). In addition, a study conducted in Iraq in 2020 shows that most women showed excellent knowledge and practice regarding bottle feeding (Al-Samarrai, Yaseen, & Jadoo, 2020).

Furthermore, another study was conducted in India in 2020. Study results show that the mothers were well-informed on feeding techniques for young children and infants, the value of colostrum, and breastfeeding. While some cultural myths are still present, most are no longer relevant. There was an information deficit regarding the beginning and making up of complementary feeding practices. Fewer people were aware of the variety of foods, the negative consequences of junk food, and the recommended complementary feeding techniques (Kamble, Kaur, Acharya, & Gupta, 2020).

In the same context, another study from India shows that a Lack of understanding exists regarding dietary diversity, societal and cultural food taboos, bottle-feeding, etc. To enhance mothers' practice and attitude toward supplementary feeding, strategies, including health education, awareness campaigns, and training programs for mothers, must be used (Waghmare, Kaple, Kale, & Katole, 2021). Moreover, another study shows that Children are more likely to have malocclusion than adults, and mothers are less aware of the condition. To avoid dental malocclusion, mothers need to be educated on proper feeding practices (Duraisamy, Pragasam, Vasavaih, & John, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a cross-sectional home-to-home survey design to assess bottle-feeding practices among caregivers in Karachi, Pakistan's Shireen Jinnah Colony community. The time duration of the study was three months, from January to March 2023. A random 30 participants were selected based on these criteria. Caregivers of infants aged 1 to 12 months. Residing in Shireen Jinnah Colony, Karachi, Pakistan, caregivers can be the mother or another sibling above 15. Besides, caregivers of infants outside the age range of 1 to 12 months and caregivers who do not meet the inclusion criteria (e.g., not being the mother or a sibling above 15). Caregivers unable or unwilling to consent to participate are excluded from the study. Trained surveyors visited the households of the selected caregivers to collect data. The study's goal, advantages, risks, and objectives regarding bottle feeding were discussed with the participants when the researchers visited their homes. While they gathered information to evaluate their participants' feeding practices, they asked to feed the infants. The consent form had to be signed by those willing to participate. The researchers started collecting data when the subjects gave their permission.

The surveyors used a standardized questionnaire adopted from the UNICIF of the UK. (UNICEF UK Baby Friendly Initiative Bottle Assessment Tool) designed to capture information on various aspects of bottle-feeding practices. The questionnaire included sections on feed preparation, responsive bottle feeding, pacing the feed, finishing the feed, expressed breast milk, and infant formula. The tool has three components. The 1st is demographic information consisting of five questions, age of the baby, age of the caregiver, relation with the baby, gender of the baby, and care give education. The 2nd component consists of four questions about the baby's general health. The 3rd component consists of 14 questions related to the bottle-feeding practice. The tool consists of a 0–2 rating scale, with 0 denoting "not performed," 1 denoting "performed unsatisfactory," and two denoting "performed satisfactory. The final score was interpreted as, Poor Practice: 0–9-mark, Moderate Practice: 10-19, and Good Practice: 20-28 marks. A pilot study was done on 10% of the total sample size, and the Cronbach alpha value was 0.92.

The collected data were entered into SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the caregivers and infants and the bottle-feeding practices. For inferential data, chi-square and ANOVA tests were used to associate demographic variables with practice scores. Study approval was obtained from the institute before conducting the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participating caregivers, ensuring their confidentiality and privacy. The caregivers were informed about the voluntary nature of their participation and their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1 shows the results of the demographic information. It reveals that out of the total infants, 66.7% are male, while 33.3% are female. Regarding age, 40.0% of the infants are between 1-3 months, while 30.0% fall into the 4-7 months and 8-12 months age ranges. As for the caregivers' age, the largest group 36.7% is between 16-20 years, 20.0% between 21-24 years, and 30.0% between 25-30 years. Caregivers aged above 30 account for 13.3%. Regarding the relationship with the infants, 46.7% are mothers, 23.3% are sisters, 13.3% are grandmothers, and 16.7% are other siblings. Regarding education, 13.3% of caregivers are illiterate, 30.0% have completed primary education, 20.0% have a middle school education, 26.7% have completed matriculation, 6.7% have completed FA/FSC, and 3.3% have a college degree.

Table 1 Result of Demographic Data

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Infant sex		
Male	20	66.7
Female	10	33.3
Infant Age		
1-3 months	12	40.0
4-7 months	9	30.0
8-12months	9	30.0
Age of the caregiver		
16-20	11	36.7
21-24	6	20.0
25-30	9	30.0
above 30	4	13.3
Relation with infant		
Mother	14	46.7
Sister	7	23.3
Grandmother	4	13.3
other siblings	5	16.7
Education of the caregivers		
illiterate	4	13.3
Primary	9	30.0
Middle	6	20.0
Matric	8	26.7
FA/FSC	2	6.7
Graduation	1	3.3

Table 2 shows the general health status of the infants. Most babies, 76.7%, have at least one soft stool daily, while 23.3% do not. In addition, out of the total, 60.0% of babies are experiencing appropriate weight gain or growth, while 40.0% are not. Moreover, a significant percentage, 63.3%, of babies are generally calm and relaxed during feeding and content afterward. However, 36.7% do not exhibit this behavior. Additionally, 56.7% of babies have normal skin color and are alert and awake for feeds, whereas 43.3% do not display these characteristics.

Table 2: General health and well-being of the infant

Statements	Frequency	Percent
At least one soft stool a day		
Yes	23	76.7
No	7	23.3
Appropriate weight gain/growth		
Yes	18	60.0
No	12	40.0
Is generally calm and relaxed when feeding and is content after most feeds		
Yes	19	63.3
No	11	36.7
Has a normal skin colour and is alert and waking for feeds		
Yes	17	56.7
No	13	43.3

Table 3 shows the overall level of practice regarding bottle feeding. According to the table, 36.7% of the individuals demonstrate Poor Practice, while 23.3% Moderate Practice and 40.0% having Good Practice

Table 3 Level of Practice Regarding Bottle Feeding

Levels of Practice	Frequency	Percent
Poor Practice	11	36.7
Moderate Practice	7	23.3
Good Practice	12	40.0

Figure 1 also shows the overall level of practice regarding bottle feeding. According to the table, 36.7% of the individuals demonstrate Poor Practice, 23.3% Moderate Practice, and 40.0% have Good Practice.

Figure 1 Levels of Practice

Table 4 examines the association between the sex of infants and the practice level of caregivers. It presents the distribution of caregivers' practice levels (Poor Practice, Moderate Practice, and Good Practice) based on the sex of the infants. The p-value of 0.018 indicates the statistical significance of this association.

Table 4 Association of Infants with Caregiver Practice

Association of Infants with Caregiver Practice					
		Levels			p-value
		Poor Practice	Moderate Practice	Good Practice	
sex	Male	7	2	11	0.018
	Female	4	5	1	
Total		11	7	12	

Table 5 examines the association between demographic variables and practice scores. It includes information on the age of caregivers, their relation with the infant, the infant's age, and the caregiver's education level. The analysis reveals a significant association between the age of caregivers and practice scores, with caregivers aged 25-30 scoring the highest p-value of 0.001. However, there is no significant association between the relation with the infant or infant age and practice scores. Similarly, the caregiver's education level does not significantly correlate with practice scores.

Table 5 Association of demographic variables with practice scores

Association of demographic variables with practice scores				
Age of the Caregivers	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value
16-20	11	6.9091	9.31080	0.001
21-24	6	17.6667	8.86942	
25-30	9	23.3333	4.97494	
above 30	4	14.5000	9.14695	
Relation with infant				
Mother	14	18.1429	9.67039	0.281
Sister	7	14.2857	10.67262	
Grandmother	4	14.5000	9.14695	
other siblings	5	7.6000	11.52389	
Infant Age				
1-3 months	12	13.8333	10.29416	0.459
4-7 months	9	18.2222	10.86022	
8-12months	9	13.3333	10.33199	
Care Givers Education				
Illiterate	4	14.5000	9.14695	0.376.
Primary	9	10.2222	10.91762	
Middle	6	14.1667	11.47897	
Matric	8	17.3750	9.37988	
FA/FSC	2	24.0000	5.65685	
Graduation	1	28.0000	.	

DISCUSSION

Even though bottle feeding is frequently used as a technique of infant feeding, caregivers often lack a thorough understanding of the practices involved (Suprabha et al., 2023). This knowledge gap makes it difficult to pinpoint problem areas and provide focused interventions to encourage the best bottle-feeding procedures. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate bottle-feeding practices among caregivers to understand the frequency of poor practices and identify variables linked to varying practice scores.

Present findings revealed that 36.7% of the individuals demonstrate Poor Practice, while 23.3% exhibit Moderate Practice. On the other hand, 40.0% are classified as having Good Practice. In this regard, another study found that the practice of bottle feeding was 46% (Taye et al., 2021). Another study from Nigeria found practice at a low level. This study highlights the need for breastfeeding education for women and communities globally, especially in developing nations. The health of mothers and children will be improved by focusing on these women (Akinyinka, Olatona, & Oluwole, 2016).

Additionally, another South African study found that the givers' knowledge and practice were poor regarding bottle feeding (Kassier & Veldman, 2013). Another study shows that practices like exclusive breastfeeding and timely supplemental feeding are inappropriate. Therefore, interventions emphasizing practical education should address the variables affecting exclusive breastfeeding (Asare, Preko, Baafi, & Dwumfour-Asare, 2018). Low socioeconomic status in developing countries or regions may have limited access to breastfeeding knowledge or resources, resulting in less-than-ideal bottle-feeding practices. These elements should be considered when designing interventions and educational initiatives to meet the needs better and overcome the obstacles of various populations (Dallak, Al-Rabeei, & Aljahmi, 2016; Kuzma, 2013).

The study revealed no significant association between the relation with the infant or infant age and practice scores. In contrast, another study found that infants aged 2–3 months have a high practice score (Taye et al., 2021). The research might have had various sample sizes or features, including varying socioeconomic or ethnic origins. These variables may affect how care is provided and affect the findings differently.

Present findings also show an association between caregivers' age and practice score. Similarly, an Indian study found the same result (Choudhary, Bankwar, & Choudhary, 2015). In contrast, other study found no association (Hassan et al., 2019). The studies may have evaluated bottle-feeding practices or calculated practice scores using various techniques. The observed connections may differ depending on the measurement methods, evaluation standards, or data collection procedures

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results indicate that a significant number of people need to enhance their caregiving practices. The highest degree of practice was demonstrated by caregivers between the ages of 25 and 30, suggesting a potential area of focus for interventions or support. Additionally, it was discovered that practice scores were correlated with the infant's sex, raising the possibility of gender-based variations in caregiving

practices. The study did not discover any statistically significant correlations regarding the infant, infant age, or caregivers' education, suggesting that these variables might not significantly impact practice scores. This is highly recommended that the same study should be conducted on a large sample size

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